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Interfaceless Exchange Bias in CoFe_2O_4 Nanocrystals

Beatriz Rivas-Murias,¹ Martín Testa-Anta,² Alexander S. Skorikov,³ Miguel Comesaña-Hermo,⁴

Sara Bals,³ Verónica Salgueiriño^{5,6}*

¹CACTI, Universidade de Vigo, 36310 Vigo (Spain)

²Institut de Ciència de Materials de Barcelona (ICMAB-CSIC), Campus de la UAB, 08193
Bellaterra (Spain)

³Electron Microscopy for Materials Research (EMAT), University of Antwerp,
Groenenborgerlaan 171, 2020 Antwerp (Belgium)

⁴Université Paris Cité, CNRS, ITODYS, Paris F-75013 Paris (France)

⁵Departamento de Física Aplicada, Universidade de Vigo, 36310 Vigo (Spain)

⁶CINBIO, Universidade de Vigo, 36310 Vigo (Spain)

Abstract

Oxidized cobalt ferrite nanocrystals with a modified distribution of the magnetic cations in their spinel structure give place to an unusual exchange-coupled system with a double reversal of the magnetization, exchange bias and increased coercivity, but without the presence of a clear physical interface that delimits two well-differentiated magnetic phases. More specifically, the partial oxidation of cobalt cations and the formation of Fe vacancies at the surface region entail the formation of a cobalt-rich mixed ferrite spinel which is strongly pinned by the ferrimagnetic background from the cobalt ferrite lattice. This particular configuration of exchange-biased magnetic behavior, involving two different magnetic phases but without the occurrence of a

crystallographically coherent interface, revolutionizes the established concept of the exchange bias phenomenology.

Keywords: Exchange bias; spinel ferrite nanocrystals; pinned and unpinned uncompensated moments; Raman spectroscopy.

The exchange bias (EB) effect, also referred to as unidirectional or exchange anisotropy, describes a magnetic coupling observed in core-shell nanocrystals (NCs) or thin films, generally between an antiferromagnet (AFM) and a ferro- or ferrimagnet (FM and FiM, respectively) separated by a physical interface.¹ The EB effect with FM/FM, FiM/FiM, AFM/AFM or FM/spin glass exchange interactions has also been reported,²⁻⁶ as well as more exotic systems stemming from interfacial spin configurations (that is, non-collinear or frustrated interface spins)⁶⁻⁸ or even in magnetic NCs holding antiphase boundaries due to their strained crystalline structure.^{9,10} Such coupling produces a horizontal shift in the hysteresis loop after cooling under an applied magnetic field, and is often accompanied by an increase in its coercive field (H_C), endorsing these systems with a huge relevance in many technological applications related to permanent magnets¹¹ or magnetic recording media.^{12,13}

Given that EB is by definition an interfacial phenomenon dependent on a physical boundary between two well-differentiated magnetic components,^{1,14} fine tuning of the dimensions, nature and overall quality of such interface is needed in order to control the magnetic coupling.^{15,16} In this context, thin interfacial layers with FM or AFM properties generated at film-substrate interfaces, driven by a structural¹⁷ or magnetic reconstruction,¹⁸ as well as spin disorder,¹⁹ can add new degrees of freedom for its engineering across heterointerfaces.

The origin of EB is known to lie on pinned uncompensated interfacial spins,²⁰ but a crucial influence of the inner (bulk) pinned uncompensated spins from the AFM component was recently demonstrated.²¹ In fact, the interfacial spin distribution can be modified by the bulk AFM magnetic landscape, for instance via non-magnetic impurities or crystallographic defects, both of them conducive to AFM order dilution and the consequent AFM domain formation.^{21,22} These

phenomena have been mostly investigated in AFM materials, but the underlying physical mechanism can be considered for their FiM counterparts.

Among the FiM candidates for the development of EB systems, combinations of different spinel ferrites stand out given their potential in spintronics.^{23,24} These spinel-type oxides are prone to disorder and exchange processes on the cation sublattices, with the normal and inverse spinel as the two limiting cases under an ordered sublattice occupation. The disorder, if controlled, can perturb the ideal local coordination, for instance by inducing charge imbalances and ion vacancies, all of this having a huge impact on the heterostructure behavior. Consequently, the electrical and magnetic properties of these ferrites and, in general, of the transition metal oxide heterostructures,^{25–27} can be modified when tailoring the interfacial and lattice characteristics through ionic motion.²⁸ Along these lines, a systematic tuning of the atomic distribution at the tetrahedral and octahedral sites of these spinel ferrites has opened new pathways for generating emergent phenomena in heterostructures due to ion migration.^{29–31} Nevertheless, some control in the ion migration is required, to avoid the otherwise deleterious effects degrading the EB.³²

Still, despite the important advances made in understanding the EB effect,^{11,31} its analysis in single-phase objects lacking a core-shell or a layered structure, that is, lacking of a physical interface between two magnetic phases, has been reported scarcely.^{10,11} Herein, we present a confined chemical treatment at the surface of single-crystallite CoFe_2O_4 NCs by which a change in the spinel crystalline structure is not appreciated but an ionic rearrangement in the subsurface and surface regions of the spherical NCs is induced. This situation offers a unique exchange coupling interaction within the same NC, without establishing a physical or coherent crystallographic interface. Yet, the magnetization reversal of the modified NCs is observed to occur in two steps and to come along with an increase in coercivity and an EB shift, suggesting the existence of a

strong exchange interaction between two magnetic components. The chemical changes registered, associated to the cation rearrangement in the spinel structure, help understand the magnetism displayed and underline the possibilities of this new chemical route for the engineering of EB-related functionalities for final device applications.

CoFe₂O₄ NCs with spherical shape and narrow size distribution (10.6 ± 1.3 nm average diameter (95.5%), log-normal fit) were synthesized by a seed-mediated growth (experimental details and Figure S1 in the Supporting Information (SI)). Figure 1a includes a TEM image of the NCs and Figure 1b shows its powder XRD pattern at room temperature, which is indexed to a cubic spinel structure (*Fd-3m* symmetry group) and allows to discard secondary phases. The cell parameter obtained from the Le Bail analysis is 0.8394 nm (see Table S1.1 in the SI), in good agreement with bulk cobalt ferrite (JCPDS card 22-1086).³³⁻³⁵ Elementary analysis using ICP-OES indicates an average Co_{0.95}Fe_{2.05}O₄ stoichiometry (from now on referred to as CoFe₂O₄). A fraction of the same batch of these CoFe₂O₄ NCs was subsequently immersed and confined in a basic aqueous medium using a water-in-oil (W/O) reverse microemulsion, that is, stabilizing them by a nonionic surfactant (Igepal® CA-520) in water droplets in a hydrophobic continuous phase.³⁶ Besides the surfactant, these water droplets of very small volume exposed the NCs to a high pH, promoting an oxidation process at their surface.^{36,37} This sample is hereafter labelled as CoFe₂O₄@Ox.

Figure 1. TEM image with general particle overview and X-ray diffraction pattern with Le Bail refinement of the CoFe_2O_4 NCs (a, b). HAADF-STEM images of representative CoFe_2O_4 (c) and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@Ox$ (e) NCs and their respective FFT images (d and f). Inset in (e): zoomed-in image of

the defect-free crystalline structure. Size histograms (fitted to log-normal functions) of CoFe_2O_4 (g) and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ (h) NCs. Hysteresis loops measured at 10 K of CoFe_2O_4 (blue) and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ (red) samples (i) and comparison of their derivatives, with μ_0H_{s1} and μ_0H_{s2} magnetic fields at which two events of magnetization switching occur (j). ZFC and FC curves measured at 10 mT (k) and distribution of energy barriers $f(T_B)$ calculated from the ZFC-FC curves and derivatives (l) of CoFe_2O_4 (blue dots) and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ (red dots) samples. Hysteresis loops measured at 10 K of the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample after ZFC (red) and FC at 5 T (gray) (m).

To shed light on the effect these conditions exert on the CoFe_2O_4 spinel structure, a high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) study of the as-synthesized (Figure 1c and d and Figure S2a and c, CoFe_2O_4 sample) and the chemically-treated (Figure 1e and f and Figure S2b and d, $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample) NCs was performed. These images show no clear differences in the crystalline structure of these representative NCs, lacking in both cases the core-shell structure expected from a superficial oxidation. Indeed, the spinel crystalline lattice highlighted at these high resolution images has not defects, dislocations or twin boundaries up to the surface. The higher resolution image included in Figure 1e, obtained along the [110] zone axis, permits to appreciate distinct contrast associated to the positions of the atomic columns, offering an enlarged view of the defect-free spinel structure in the whole nanocrystal from the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample. Interestingly, we can appreciate neither Moiré fringes nor grain or antiphase boundaries.³⁸ Moreover, the size histogram of the samples (fitted to log-normal function) does not show apparent modifications either (Figures 1g and 1h), and the analysis of atomic column positions in a 2D projection of a $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ NC shows the absence of systematic strain fields (Figure S3), thus excluding the presence of interfacial strain between two crystalline phases.

Yet, the magnetic behavior of the two CoFe_2O_4 and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ samples points to an important change in the configuration of the magnetic cations in the spinel structure. Figure 1i includes the comparison of the magnetic properties displayed by the as-synthesized CoFe_2O_4 sample (blue curve) and by the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample (red curve) at 10 K. The value of maximum magnetization registered for the CoFe_2O_4 sample is $\sim 87 \text{ Am}^2/\text{kg}$ when applying the maximum field (7 T), close to that of the bulk cobalt ferrite saturation magnetization ($M_{\text{S(bulk)}} \sim 90 \text{ Am}^2/\text{kg}$)³⁹ and similar to others values reported for NCs.^{40,41} This is in agreement with the very good crystallinity of the NCs observed by HAADF-STEM and the stoichiometry registered. Anyhow, different effects related to a canted surface spin structure,⁴² a gradient in the magnetic cations ratio moving outwards from the core to the surface,^{43–45} or a cationic disorder in the crystalline structure at the surface can explain the slight difference. While this value of M_{S} when applying the maximum 7 T field drops to $\sim 45 \text{ Am}^2/\text{kg}$ for the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample, the coercive field value increases ($\mu_0 H_{\text{C}} = 1.06 \text{ T}$ and $\mu_0 H_{\text{C}} = 1.26 \text{ T}$ for CoFe_2O_4 and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ samples, respectively). In both cases, these high values of $\mu_0 H_{\text{C}}$ are related to the high magnetostriction of CoFe_2O_4 , due to the strong spin-orbit coupling from the Co^{2+} ions in the crystalline lattice.^{43,46} In addition, the shape of the hysteresis loop has evolved after the chemical microemulsion-based treatment, with two reversals of magnetization (one of them much larger), seen as two inflection points ($\mu_0 H_{\text{S1}}$ and $\mu_0 H_{\text{S2}}$ magnetic fields) around 5 and 10 mT and 1.14 and 1.55 T when comparing the derivatives (dM/dH), shown in Figure 1j. The significantly larger reversal contribution at low field in the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample clearly hints that a cationic modification took place. Similar contributions at low field were reported in samples of CoFe_2O_4 NCs synthesized by a co-precipitation method under alkaline conditions,^{34,47,48} where phase segregation (due to Co_3O_4 and/or Fe_2O_3) or a phase with a reduced crystallinity was formed, but not detected in our samples in STEM. Figure 1k

displays the temperature dependent magnetization curves, measured under ZFC (zero-field cooled) and FC (field cooled) conditions and recorded applying a field of 10 mT. Whereas the mass magnetization value of the CoFe₂O₄@Ox has decreased notably in comparison to that of the initial sample (in line with the hysteresis loops), the shape of the ZFC and FC curves is very similar. Based on these ZFC-FC curves, it is possible to estimate the energy barrier distribution (in terms of the blocking temperature, T_B: $f(T_B) \propto (1/T) [d(M_{ZFC}-M_{FC})/dT]$),⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ fitted to a log-normal function in agreement with the size distribution, see Figures 1g, 1h and 1i). The average T_B values obtained are very similar, 265 and 262 K for CoFe₂O₄ and CoFe₂O₄@Ox samples, respectively, and comparable to other values of the literature.^{40,52-54} This match in the blocking temperature reflects the very similar magnetically coherent volumes of FiM material in both samples,⁵⁵ despite the fact of observing two reversals of magnetization. Such finding is in line with the absence of an interface or any other crystalline defect in the crystalline structure, and the absence of byproducts (smaller nanoparticles and/or low anisotropy magnetic phases).

In order to further analyze the switching behavior in the CoFe₂O₄@Ox sample in terms of exchange-coupling properties, we measured the hysteresis loops in ZFC and FC conditions applying an external magnetic field of 5 T (Figure 1m). Though there is a decrease in coercivity, the FC hysteresis loop shows a negative field shift ($\mu_0 H_E = -56.9$ mT) associated to an EB effect. Such coupling, usually attributed to a FM/AFM interaction, is strong enough to produce a unidirectional anisotropy that causes the observed shift. The reduced coercivity registered for the CoFe₂O₄@Ox sample under FC conditions (compared to the ZFC loop) also unveils a reduction of the effective magnetic anisotropy, likely induced by the large cooling field. Similar trends have been reported in previous studies and ascribed to AFM order frustration.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ In our case, this observation can be understood considering the presence of pinned uncompensated spins, which

align with the sufficiently large cooling field employed and induce frustration of the FiM exchange coupling. The presence of this hypothesized larger number of pinned uncompensated moments is supported experimentally by the large drop in the saturation magnetization but increased coercivity. Overall, these results point to a crucial influence of the synthetic conditions on the magnetic behavior of the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample with respect to the as-synthesized one.

Aiming to corroborate the idea of the confined chemical effect in the micelles as the origin of the change in the magnetic behavior observed for the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample, we performed an additional mapping of Fe and Co distribution and investigated their electronic configuration using electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS). Figure 2a shows elemental mapping for CoFe_2O_4 and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ samples, which indicates a similar increasing concentration of Co towards the surface of the nanocrystal in both cases. Although we cannot completely exclude an effect of electron beam irradiation, the results of different experimental techniques corroborate that CoFe_2O_4 or MnFe_2O_4 NCs synthesized via thermal decomposition typically have an increased content of Co or Mn at their surface, owing to the different decomposition temperature of the metallic precursors.^{43–45,59} In this regard, the hysteresis loops of the initial sample show a very small reversal of magnetization at low field which can stem from the cobalt patches observed at the surface, and present in both native and oxidized samples. Anyway, the very large value of coercivity registered at low temperature can only be associated to the $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ stoichiometry, even with increasing values of x as moving outwards. Additionally, EELS spectra of L edges for Fe and Co in CoFe_2O_4 and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ samples (Figure 2b) reveal that: a) the L edge of Co in $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ is shifted by *ca.* +1.0 eV in comparison to CoFe_2O_4 , indicating an increase in the oxidation state of Co, resulting from the chemical treatment,^{60,61} and b) the ratio between the Fe L_3 and Co L_3 edges decreases from 2.95 in the CoFe_2O_4 sample to 2.59 in the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$

sample, indicating an average decrease in the iron content. These experimental results point to a partial oxidation of cobalt cations and the formation of Fe vacancies in the spinel structure at the subsurface region, providing an explanation for the presence of pinned uncompensated moments associated to the changes in the magnetic behavior of the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample and, particularly, to the EB effect.

Figure 2. (a) Mapping of Fe and Co distribution in CoFe_2O_4 and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ NCs based on EELS. (b) Comparison of EELS spectra for L edges of Fe and Co between CoFe_2O_4 and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ samples. The dashed lines in the Co L_3 edge point out the shift of the edge position after oxidation. (c) Stokes-shifted Raman spectra registered using a 785 nm excitation wavelength from the CoFe_2O_4 (blue curve) and the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ (red curve) samples.

To further support this relationship, we performed a Raman analysis of the as-synthesized CoFe_2O_4 and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ samples in order to investigate the chemical/structural origin of the peculiar magnetic features observed.⁶² This technique can register six Raman active modes from the spinel structure, namely $2A_{1g}$, E_g , and $3T_{2g}$, characteristic of spinels with two different types of cations occupying the octahedral or tetrahedral sites, such as CoFe_2O_4 (see Figure S4 in the SI).⁶³ In general, the ferrite A_{1g} modes appear above 600 cm^{-1} and are usually assigned to the motion of oxygen in the tetrahedral AO_4 group along the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction, involving a symmetric stretching of the oxygen atoms with respect to the metal ion at the tetrahedral void (T),⁶⁴ as well as the deformation of the three octahedral sites (O) nearest to each oxygen.⁶⁵ Figure 2c includes the Raman spectra registered. In the as-synthesized sample (blue spectrum) the expected modes for the spinel lattice are observed,⁶⁶ with the most intense peak at 679 cm^{-1} ($A_{1g}(2)$) and a small shoulder at $\sim 620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($A_{1g}(1)$), which stem from the presence of Fe^{3+} and Co^{2+} ions at the tetrahedral sites, respectively.^{65,67} Note that the $A_{1g}(1)$ mode intensity is much lower than that of $A_{1g}(2)$, meaning that the primary contribution to the AO_4 vibrations originates from the Fe^{3+} ions. There is less consensus regarding the origin of the other low-frequency modes (E_g and T_{2g}), typically assigned to the tetrahedral unit in the Fe_3O_4 material,^{64,68} or to the octahedral unit when considering mixed spinel ferrites such as CoFe_2O_4 or ZnFe_2O_4 .^{69,70} In the latter case, the E_g vibrational mode has been assigned to the symmetric bending of oxygen with respect to Fe in the octahedral BO_6 void⁶⁴ and is usually absent in nanocrystals.⁷¹ The fact that this mode can be ascertained in our spectrum underlines once again the optimal crystallinity of the CoFe_2O_4 NCs. On the other hand, the $T_{2g}(2)$ mode has been reported to account solely for the Co^{2+} ions occupying the octahedral sites.⁷² Hence, the higher intensity of the $T_{2g}(2)$ and the $A_{1g}(2)$ modes compared to

the $A_{1g}(1)$ mode confirms the predominant inverse spinel configuration anticipated for the cobalt ferrite.

The characteristic features of the spinel crystalline structure are still present in the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ spectrum (red curve). However, the relative intensities of the A_{1g} and T_{2g} vibration modes have notably changed; being the $T_{2g}(2)$ mode (at $\sim 470\text{ cm}^{-1}$) the most prominent feature in the Raman spectrum. Interestingly, the vibrational modes $T_{2g}(3)$ and $A_{1g}(1)$ begin to merge into one broad band owing to the pronounced red-shift of the $A_{1g}(1)$ mode, now located at $\sim 600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (see also Figure S4). This shift is usually associated to structural distortions and/or the presence of a different set of cations at the tetrahedral/octahedral sites. Taking into account the absence of strain fields (Figure S3) and the *ca.* +1.0 eV shift observed in the Co L edge from the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample (compared to CoFe_2O_4) (Figure 2b), the red-shift of the $A_{1g}(1)$ mode is consistent with the presence of Co^{3+} cations within the spinel structure, in addition to Fe^{3+} and Co^{2+} .⁶⁷ The resultant charge compensation of the crystalline structure may proceed via Fe vacancies⁷³ or a partial $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ reduction. While the presence of Fe^{3+} vacancies is supported by the decrease in the Fe/Co L_3 ratio registered, which indicates a reduced iron content in the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample with respect to the pristine sample, the partial $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ reduction seems less probable, given the absence of observable changes in the L edge of the Fe spectrum in the EELS analysis. The fact that we have not registered the vacancies in the HAADF-STEM analysis suggests that their content must be rather small. Along these lines, the decrease in the $A_{1g}(2)$ mode intensity can be explained by this chemical and local modification promoted by the Fe^{3+} vacancies created. The oxidation of some of the Co^{2+} ions to Co^{3+} and the changes associated to the Fe^{3+} ions raise the question whether a non-stoichiometric $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\cdot\text{O}_4$ spinel is formed at the subsurface region, but since the HAADF-STEM analysis reveals no evidence of two crystallographic phases at the core and the

surface shell, the as-formed mixed ferrite spinel must be highly disordered in terms of the metallic cation distribution. This disorder is also hinted by the presence of additional features in the Raman spectrum of the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample, displaying new modes of low intensity at 420 and 760 cm^{-1} , for instance.

An additional experiment registering the evolution of the Raman spectra as a function of the incident laser power was also performed for the two CoFe_2O_4 and $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ systems (Figure S5). The Raman spectrum of the as-synthesized sample evolves into the same signature observed for $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ when treated under a laser power of 5.82 mW (Figure S5a), which can be associated to a partial oxidation of Co^{2+} cations reported above.⁷⁴ Furthermore, the very similar spectra recorded at 0.42 mW , after subjecting both samples to the highest laser power (21 mW) (Figure S5a and b), exhibit a remarked increase in the $T_{2g}(2)$ mode intensity compared to the $A_{1g}(2)$ mode, in agreement with a reduced iron content due to Fe^{3+} vacancy formation. The presence of these vacancies can be understood as a preliminary step prior to the transformation toward maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), and is also corroborated by the blue-shift of the $A_{1g}(2)$ mode to $\sim 690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (note that the A_{1g} mode characteristic from maghemite occurs at $\sim 700\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Conclusively, to explain the coupling mechanism and the local magnetic configuration given the chemical changes registered by EELS and Raman spectroscopy and given the fact that there is no crystallographically coherent interface, we take the coercivity of the initial CoFe_2O_4 NCs as reference ($\mu_0 H_C = 1.06\text{ T}$). With this large value into account, the fraction of CoFe_2O_4 phase at the outer shell of the as-synthesized NCs switches readily ($\mu_0 H_{S1} = 5\text{ mT}$) (Figure 1j). However, for the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample, while the magnetic phase at the subsurface region now switches with a value of $\mu_0 H_{S1} = 10\text{ mT}$, the CoFe_2O_4 phase at the core follows an even larger switching field ($\mu_0 H_{S2} = 1.55\text{ T}$). This can be explained considering the presence of unpinned uncompensated

moments in the cation disordered subsurface region of the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample, which couple to the external field and rotate along with the FiM CoFe_2O_4 core, resulting in a coercivity enhancement.^{21,22} On the other hand, the rather strong negative $\mu_0 H_E$ field (-56.9 mT) indicates the presence of pinned uncompensated moments that strongly couple to the FiM lattice but do not rotate even at the maximum field (7 T). The presence of these pinned and unpinned magnetic moments can be understood as the outcome of competing interactions within the parental spinel structure, where the Co^{2+} oxidation has the Fe-O-Fe and Co-O-Fe superexchange interactions disrupted, leading to a highly frustrated subsurface region. This increased magnetic frustration, boosted by the assumed cation disorder, is reflected not only in the drop in the value of magnetization down to $45 \text{ Am}^2/\text{kg}$ (which can be explained by the presence of low-spin Co^{3+} on octahedral sites⁷⁵), but also in the low-anisotropy component detected during the reversal of the $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{Ox}$ sample. This fact hints that, besides inducing magnetic disorder, some short-range correlated spin disorder occurs. This situation, particularly in terms of the effects stemming from the presence of Co^{3+} and the iron vacancies, inducing a charge reorganization, with local modifications of the valence charge states and possible creation of defect gap states, can explain the changes not only in the magnetization, but also in the electronic, ionic and tunnel conductivities.⁷⁶ Such effects require a more in-depth investigation that falls out of the scope of the present study. Alternative scenarios in the attained cation distribution at the subsurface, such as a change from an inverse to a normal spinel configuration,^{77,78} would lead to a magnetization enhancement and can be therefore discarded.

Summarizing, whereas the HAADF-STEM images show NCs with a uniform crystalline structure up to the surface and without the presence of defects or strain, both EELS and Raman spectroscopy, jointly with the magnetic properties, point to the presence of a pseudo core-shell structure with no

physical interface. Such unusual characteristics render the system particularly fascinating, pointing to a interfaceless exchange coupling between two different distributions of magnetic cations within the parent spinel structure.

Additional information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: XXXX. Experimental methods; supplementary Le Bail refinement data, HAADF-STEM data, strain analysis; supplementary magnetic data and supplementary Raman spectroscopy analysis.

Author information

Corresponding authors

*E-mail: vsalgue@uvigo.es

ORCID

Beatriz Rivas-Murias: 0000-0002-8048-5364

Martín Testa-Anta: 0000-0003-4437-2589

Alexander S. Skorikov: 0000-0001-8870-5344

Miguel Comesaña-Hermo: 0000-0001-8471-5510

Sara Bals: 0000-0002-4249-8017

Verónica Salgueiriño: 0000-0002-9396-468X

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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